

CERTAINTY LU's DMP

Version 0

Description

The Data Management Plan (DMP) for global climate model data created at Lund University is developed in the context of effectively managing and preserving valuable data generated for CERTAINTY project.

The DMP for global climate model data at Lund University is designed to maximize the value, accessibility, and impact of the data produced, supporting the Institute's mission in advancing meteorological research and services.

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CERTAINTY

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Organizations

Lund University, Lund, Sweden

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [CERTAINTY LU's DMP](#)

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Organizations:

[Lund University, Lund, Sweden](#)

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: [European Commission|EC](#)

Grants: [CERTAINTY](#)

Project: [CERTAINTY](#)

3. License

License: [CC-BY-4.0](#)

Access Rights: [Public](#)

4. Templates

Descriptions

NorESM output

The dataset will consist of simulations performed with the Earth System Model NorESM (Norwegian Earth System Model) within the Horizon Europe project certainty. The purpose of these simulations will be to advance the understanding of aerosol-cloud-climate interactions.

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Simulation

The data will consist of PRIMARY data from model simulations

1.1.5 What is its format?

netcdf

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

2 TB, 3000 files

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To share information
- To make informed decisions
- To combine with other data

Data will be used to study processes, interpret observations, and constrain aerosol-cloud interactions.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

The origin of the data is NorESM <https://www.noresm.org>, <https://noresm-docs.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers
- Education

Project partners

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

DataCite Metadata Schema

zenodo.org

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

Descriptive

Zenodo offer descriptive metadata that enriches data or information resources with detailed information about their content, context, and structure, thereby improving their findability and practical use.

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.1.1.7 How are searchable metadata provided?

- Registry/Catalogue
- Metadata repository

Beyond generating descriptive metadata, the indexed metadata is incorporated into search engines like OPENAIRE Explore and the EOSC-portal. This metadata will undergo regular reviews, updates, and management to maintain its accuracy and relevance, especially as changes occur in the data collection, such as the addition, modification, or removal of data items.

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

OAI-PMH

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Zenodo

zenodo.org

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

- Follows repository standards
- Details terms of use
- Has an open access content policy
- Supports retention

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.6 Does the repository(ies) resolve the identifiers to a digital object?

Zenodo provides DOIs

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

NorESM output

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

Open, although a certain embargo period might be applied

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

Throughout the project's duration, the dataset might be subject to an embargo of up to two years. During this period, access to the data will be restricted, but project partners can obtain access using specific tokens. Once the embargo period concludes and the project is completed, the dataset will become publicly available, and accessible to all under the CC BY 4.0 license.

After the data become publicly accessible, it will not be possible to identify individuals who access the data. However, during the embargo period, access is controlled through tokens that are nominally issued to specific, selected partners.

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

Long-term accessibility

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

Yes. However, we will not have closed datasets

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

Direct links are provided

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

Yes

DataCite Metadata Schema

3.3.7 Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?

Yes

The dataset will be linked with the related scientific articles and also with other datasets.

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

The embargo period (if needed) is a maximum of 2 years from publication.

3.4.2 What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?

- Readme files
- Codebooks
- Data cleaning
- Analyses
- Variable definitions
- Units of measurement
- Negative results sharing

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

Input data provenance will be linked in the metadata.

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

Use of tools for automatic checks

We will use automatic tests to make sure that the NorESM model is running as required

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

- Storage
- Re-use

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

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5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 What security measures are followed?

Passwords

5.1.2 What conditions do the security measures meet?

- Data access
- Data storage
- Data transmission
- Data recovery
- Data sharing

5.1.3 How will you preserve the described dataset / output in the long term?

Zenodo will keep the published data available data long-term. The unpublished data will not be stored long-term since the output is very large and simulations can be run again with the model (open source).

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

Yes

7.1.2 Documentation of other procedures

All the minimum conditions listed in Science Europe Guidance Document are covered by the WP6 Open Science and Data management

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